

Test rig for bone screw insertion modelling

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Abstract: Bone screws are used for fixing implants and stabilizing fractures. Correct torquing of these screws is important for positive patient outcome. A previously proposed model-based system may increase the accuracy of bone screw insertion; however, all models require experimental testing to verify their accuracy and precision under real-world conditions. To test these models, a test rig was developed to insert screws into test samples while recording several variables (torque, angular displacement, and linear displacement). This rig was used to record data from screw insertions, which matched expectations. Some potential improvements have been discussed, such as adding axial force measurement.

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I. Introduction

Bone screws are commonly used in orthopedic surgery to fix implants in place or stabilize fractured bones. Over- or under-torquing these screws can lead to thread stripping or insufficient fixation, respectively; both may cause implant failure and/or tissue damage, which may cause additional complications or necessitate revision surgery. Hence, correct torquing of bone screws is important for positive patient outcomes.

Bone screws are often tightened in an ad-hoc manner. This is generally successful, but misjudgment may result in inappropriate tightening torques. Varying surgeon skill and experience levels may lead to additional inconsistencies[1]. It has been proposed that a model-based method can be used to identify the material properties of bone during the screw insertion process[2], and that these properties can then be used to recommend or enforce optimal insertion torques. If successful, this could reduce fixation failures and increase the probability of positive patient outcomes.

While a number of models have been proposed so far[2], [3], these must still be tested. To do so, an experimental test setup was required. This test rig is described in this paper, in terms of the individual components and their integration.

II. Material and methods

The test rig shown in Fig. 1 is designed to primarily measure the angular displacement and torque of the screw; which have been the variables used in modelling so far[2], [3]. Additionally, it measures linear displacement to detect when the screw engages in the hole (when linear and angular velocity become proportional). Finally, it has a powerful stepper motor to insert the screw in a controlled manner using arbitrary speed profiles. This is mounted on a carriage on linear bearings to allow the motor and sensors to move while screwing into the test material, which is clamped in place. A control box contains a microcontroller (TM4C123GH6PM, Texas Inst.), power supply (48VDC 7.3A max.), and stepper motor driver (CL86T, OMC Corp. Ltd.); this controls the motor and processes data from the sensors, which is then sent over a USB COM port to a PC.

Figure 1. Test rig setup. (A)Torque Sensor. (B)Draw wire encoder (wire connected to clamp). (C)Stepper motor. (D)Carriage with linear bearings. (E)Linear rails. (F)Clamp and test piece (G)Screwdriver bit/holder. (H)Inclined platform. Control box not shown.

II.I Sensors

There are two main sensors on the test rig measuring 3 variables. A torque sensor measures the torque being applied to the screw, and the angular displacement of the shaft. A draw wire encoder measures the linear displacement of the carriage (roughly equal to the linear displacement of screw). The stepper motor also contains an encoder for closed-loop control, however it is not recorded.

The torque sensor (A (in Fig. 1)) is an NCTE-2300-20-1-AU-0-0(NCTE AG); with a range of $-20\text{Nm} - 20\text{Nm}$. This sensor outputs via USB (unused), and a $0-10\text{V}$ analog signal which is digitized then filtered by the control box. This sensor also outputs a 360 counts per revolution (CPR) (1440 with quadrature) incremental angular displacement signal.

The displacement sensor (B) is an A40/D5.2501.2421.1000 (Fritz Kübler GmbH). This is an incremental draw-wire encoder with 1000 CPR (4000 with quadrature), and a 100mm circumference spool, giving a resolution of 0.1 mm (0.025 with quadrature).

II.II. Motion

To drive the screw into the test material consistently with arbitrary speed profiles, a high-torque closed-loop stepper motor was used. The stepper motor (C) (34HS46-6004D-E100, OMC Corp. Ltd.) has an 8.25 Nm stall torque, and due to the closed loop control, can maintain a high torque and accuracy at moderate speed (e.g., over 5.5Nm at 150 RPM/48V).

This motor was coupled to the torque sensor, which was in turn coupled to a $\frac{1}{4}$ inch hexagonal screw bit holder (G). Any screwdriver bit can then be used to drive screws into test samples, allowing a variety of screws to be tested.

The sensors and motor are mounted on an aluminum plate/carriage(D), which slides along linear rails(E) (SME 16 UU (0.45m length), Tuli d.o.o.) using linear bearings (SA 16, Tuli d.o.o.). The rails are mounted on a wooden platform(H), which is inclined at an angle just high enough to overcome the friction of the bearings and cause the carriage to slide towards the sample unassisted.

II.III Clamp and Sample

For securing the test samples in place, a wooden clamp(F) is used. The base block raises the material up to the height of the shaft on the carriage. This block is 97mm high, and the shaft is 105mm high (from the wooden base), so predrilled holes in the samples are made at 8mm from the edge for optimal alignment.

To ensure the samples are perpendicular to the screw, a back piece is attached to the base block. When samples are pushed against this, they are aligned perpendicularly, and a parallel spacer can be used for shallower samples.

Lastly, a wooden sheet is used on top to clamp and hold the test sample in place. This is large and flat to spread the force and reduce damage to the sample. The screws holding the clamp screw into threaded inserts in the base block to prevent thread stripping of the relatively soft wood, and washers spread the load on the clamp, therefore maximizing clamping force and stability.

III. Results and discussion

The raw data from a screw insertion is shown in Fig 2. The rotational displacement is triangular as this is controlled by the powerful closed-loop stepper motor. The linear displacement closely follows this but has some differences where the screw enters/exits the material, and at $\sim 12\text{s}$ when the initial axial force to engage the screw was removed. The torque is also mostly proportional to rotation, but with some curvature, and a drop when stopped at $\sim 25\text{s}$.

Figure 2. Recorded torque, angular displacement, and linear displacement from screw insertion.

While the test rig works well for its intended purpose, improvements are possible. Slack in the shaft couplings results in an imperfect measurement of rotation and linear displacement (notably when axial force is applied). Flex in the wooden base may lead to some minor inaccuracies. Addition of axial force measurement may also prove useful for later modelling, and/or for compensating for slack.

IV. Conclusions

A test rig was developed for the purpose of testing bone screw process models. This can collect the required data, however some improvements may be possible in the future.

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